

Fabrication and Studies on Microstructure, XRD and Properties of Nano Copper Alloys

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ABSTRACT

Nano materials result from the grain size of the polycrystalline materials being reduced through different processing techniques. During the process dimensional change takes place on the order of nano materials corresponding to large increase in the volume fraction of grain boundaries. Most of the processing and consolidation challenges that have really hunted nanocrystalline materials are now totally understood. Recent advances in theoretical computation and experimental capabilities have allowed mechanical alloying in powder processing technique in solid state form using harder balls (Agate) in ball milling. Micro alloying can enhance the corrosion resistant properties (1) besides enhancement of mechanical properties. The following nano copper alloys have been synthesized through the special metallurgical technique and several characteristic properties of the materials are studied.

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|-------------|-----------------------|-------------------------|
| 1. Cu-Zn-Pb | 2. Cu-Zn-Al | 3. Cu-Sn-Ag |
| 4. Cu-Sn-Fe | 5. Nano porous copper | 6. Nano copper crystals |

Mechanical properties of wire type nano materials are measured (Tensile Test). Electrical conductivity at ambient temperature and at different higher temperatures is measured. Small addition of metal oxides like Lanthanum (anti corrosion properties), Cerium (Grain reinforcement agent) (2) are very interesting in nano alloys. Stabilization of microstructure takes place during the synthesis with additives. High mechanical properties at elevated temperature and, increase of the strength of alloy is quite observable in nano copper alloys with additives like Al, Zn, Ag, Pb, etc. Additives are also useful in deoxidization process and purification of metal baths during the process of melting.

**Key Words: Nano copper, Copper Alloys, Microstructure, Corrosion resistance,
Mechanical Properties**

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